

Interview Questions

Demographics

- 1) Could you please introduce yourself a little bit?

Threat hunters' tasks

- 1) What does it mean to be a threat hunter?
- 2) Could you describe your most recent working day? Is this a typical day? Why?/Why not? How is your typical working day?
- 3) What was your most recent incident about?
- 4) What are your most common tasks as a threat hunter?
- 5) What are the most common mistakes threat hunters could potentially make?
- 6) How does the Threat Hunting Team deal with a security incident when it is discovered? Is there any systematic process? What are the steps?
- 7) Do you hunt for multiple clients?
- 8) Do you have different techniques when working with clients in different industries? For which industries?
- 9) What are the challenges/barriers you face when performing threat hunting tasks? Have you ever felt frustrated when performing threat hunting tasks? What happened? (Organizational, technical/process, human stakeholders, tools, resources, learning, etc.)
- 10) How would you mitigate those challenges?
- 11) How often do you need to switch to a different task when performing threat hunting tasks? Why?
- 12) What are the causes of interruptions while you're performing threat hunting tasks?
- 13) What would you suggest to improve the productivity/effectiveness of threat hunters?

Tooling

- 1) Could you describe your work environment? (Hardware)
- 2) What technical and non-technical tools do you usually use in your threat hunting activities? Are they always available? (Non-technical tools such as whiteboard with sticky notes, notebooks, wall maps, etc. technical tools such as SIEM tools, open source tools). Could you describe them?
- 3) Do the tools you have used during your threat-hunting activities provide some visualization techniques to support you? Which ones? (please indicate the tools and techniques)
- 4) What are the advantages of using those tools? How do they facilitate your work?
- 5) Are there any disadvantages of using them? Which ones?
- 6) What would you suggest to improve those tools? What is missing in your current tools compared to other tools you have used in the past?

Resources / Information needs

- 1) What resources (tutorials, sites, references, communities, social media) do you usually use/access while performing threat hunting activities? Are they always available?

- 2) Could you describe them? How often do you use them? In which scenarios?
- 3) How do you use those resources? Are there any limitations?
- 4) (If not mentioned in Q1 or Q2) What resources (or communities) from the dark web do you usually use/access while performing threat hunting activities?
- 5) What would you suggest to improve the use of those resources?
- 6) (If not mentioned in Q1 or Q2) How often do you approach online communities? Why? (Forums, mailing lists, meetups, etc.)

Collaboration

- 1) What are the internal collaborators you usually interact with as part of your threat hunting tasks? Are they usually available?
- 2) What are the external collaborators you usually interact with as part of your threat hunting tasks? Are they usually available? (e.g., customers)
- 3) How do you collaborate with them? Is it an ad-hoc or systematic process?
- 4) How often do you collaborate with them?
- 5) What tools do you usually use for collaboration?
- 6) How do you hand over at the end of your shift? Can you describe the process?
- 7) How do you communicate information to your managers, specifically?
- 8) What will help you improve your collaboration with other peers?
- 9) How could your organization help you improve that collaboration?

Learning

- 1) What are the core skills (technical and not technical) to be a threat hunter?
- 2) How was your personal journey to become a threat hunter? (Mentors, role models?).
- 3) What practices do you usually follow to keep-up-to-date your cyber security knowledge? Could you describe your strategy for learning? (Learning by doing, self-taught, trial and error, on the fly education, etc.)
- 4) What does it take for a threat hunter to become confident in performing threat hunting tasks?
- 5) How is knowledge disseminated across threat hunting teams and other stakeholders?
- 6) Do you find it challenging transferring your expertise? Why?

Situational Awareness

The first two questions are to do with the elements of the threat hunting environment like tools, resources of information, or anything else you might access to deal with a security incident.

- 1) When you are handling a security incident, what are the elements that you need to understand that incident?
- 2) How do you use the elements of your environment to understand the security incident?

- 3) How do you know the urgency of a security incident? and How do you differentiate between different security incidents?
- 4) How do you anticipate future threats and their implications? (individual's ability to project forward in time to anticipate future events, i.e., if the current sequence of suspicious events continues, and they're coming from the same source, then the next likely event will be of a specific type)
- 5) What criterion do you usually use when evaluating the urgency of different security incidents?

Situational Awareness (Use of X Tool)

- 1) From 1 to 5 (5=very satisfied) If applicable, how satisfied or dissatisfied are you with the visualizations in the tool? Why?
- 2) From 1 to 5, How satisfied or dissatisfied are you with the visualizations in the tool for communicating with internal collaborators? Why?
- 3) From 1 to 5, How satisfied or dissatisfied are you with the visualizations in the tool for communicating with external collaborators? Why?
- 4) From 1 to 5, How satisfied or dissatisfied are you with the visualizations in the tool for investigating? Why?
- 5) From 1 to 5, How satisfied or dissatisfied are you with the visualizations in the tool for exploring? Why?
- 6) From 1 to 5, How satisfied or dissatisfied are you with the visualizations in the tool for breach anticipation? Why?

Behavioral Threat Hunter Persona

- 1) From 1 to 5 (5=highly confident). How confident do you feel about performing threat hunting tasks? Why?
- 2) How would you describe the mindset of a threat hunter? (Analytical mindset, adept at solo work, satisfaction from being the last line of defense, inquisitive personality? etc.)
- 3) What are your motivations for being a threat hunter?
- 4) What are your personal goals as a threat hunter? What makes you a successful threat hunter? Which goals are most important to you? Why?
- 5) What types of rewards or incentives positively influence your work as a threat hunter? Does your organization have any metrics for measuring threat hunting capabilities? Which ones?
- 6) What type of cultural factors do you believe might influence your work as a threat hunter? Why? (Language, norms, values, ethics, attitudes, age, gender etc.)

Figure 1: Thomas' persona profile.

Figure 2: Jay's persona profile.

Figure 3: Olivia's persona profile.

Figure 4: Ren's persona profile.

Participant	P1	P2	P3	P4	M5	M6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	M13	P14	P15	P16	P17
Educational Background																	
High School								•					•				
College					•				•							•	
Bachelor's Degree	•	•				•	•			•							•
Master's Degree			•								•	•		•	•		
Ph.D. or Higher				•													
Years of Work Experience in Security																	
0 to 5	•	•						•									
6 to 10			•				•			•	•			•	•		•
11 to 15									•								
16 to 20				•	•												
21 to 30												•	•				
31+						•										•	
Time in Current Threat Hunting Role																	
0 to 2	•	•	•				•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•		
3 to 5				•	•				•								•
6 to 10						•											
11+																•	
Industry																	
Information Services and Technology			•			•	•	•		•	•			•		•	•
Enterprise Software	•	•															
Financial Services, Banking and Insurance				•											•		
Government					•								•				
Cybersecurity									•								
Semiconductor												•					
Work Location																	
Remote	•	•	•			•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	na		•
Hybrid				•	•		•						•		na	•	
Affiliation Type																	
Consultant	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Internal													•		•		
Freelancer				•													

TABLE 1: Summary of participant demographics. “M” indicates a manager. “na” indicates no answer provided.

Non-Technical Tools		
Antivirus	Internet	Shared drive for documents
Cherwell	JIRA	Signal
Client environment tools	MS teams	Skype
Confluence	Notepad/Notebook	Slack
Discord	Notepad++	Sublime Text
Email	OneNote	TextPad
Evernote	Outlook	Up notes
Excel	Password manager	VS Code
FreshService	Pen/marker	WhatsApp
GLIP	PowerPoint	Whiteboard
Google doc	RingCentral	Word
Intake form for client called-in incidents.	Screenshot	Zoom

TABLE 2: List of non-technical tools used by threat hunters

Tool Type	Names
Command Line Tools	Chainsaw, CyberChef, NMap, Kansa, theHarvester
Logging	Sysinternals, Hayabusa
IP and File Checking	VirusTotal, AbuseIPDB, IPVoid, Excel
Network Visibility	Procmon, PRTG, Fiddler, Security Onion, WireShark, RedSeal
Automation and Scripting	Power Automate, Jupyter Notebooks, Autoruns, Python, ServiceNow
Intrusion Detection	Checkpoint
Code Vulnerability	Fortify, Veracode, Snyk
Endpoint Detection and Management	Tanium, CarbonBlack, CrowdStrike
Malware Analysis	Any Run, Malware Bazaar, Cuckoo, Joe Sandbox
Virtual Environment	AnyConnect, Citrix, Tor, TeamViewer, Parrot OS, FlareVM, LogMeIn, Tails
SIEM and SOAR	Azure Sentinel, ArcSight, IBM, QRadar, LogRhythm, Splunk, Exabeam, Elastic, Elk Stack
Threat Hunting Platforms	FireEye, Cyborg, ArcSight
Data Loss Prevention	Proofpoint, Forcepoint
Threat Intelligence and Reconnaissance	Spiderfoot, Mandiant, Shodan, CrowdStrike, Fireeye, Rapid7, ICMX-Force

TABLE 3: Summary of technical tools used by threat hunters interviewed.

Resources		
Anomali	Google	Slack channels
Articles	LinkedIn	SOC Prime
Blogs	Local cyber security group	SpiceWorks
Books	Mastodon	Stack Overflow
Business Continuity Plan	MISP	Third party information from the dark web
Cisco Talos	Mitre	Threat Intel feeds
Conventions	Newsletters	Threat Intel team
CrowdStrike reports	OSINT	Threat intelligence platform
CyberReason	OWASP	Tool manuals or documentation
Dark web (forums)	Palo Alto unit 42	Udemy
Digital Shadows	Password disclosure lists or breaches	Vendor websites
Discord servers	Peers in their degree program	Websites / Internet – unspecified
Facebook groups	Playbooks	X (Twitter)
Feeds from external researchers	Podcasts	X-Force
Forums	Reddit	YouTube

TABLE 4: Summary of resources used by threat hunters interviewed

	Organizational Affiliation Type	Internal	The threat Hunter hunts for the organization by which they are employed.
		External	The threat Hunter hunts for clients outside of the organization by which they are employed.
	Affiliation Type	Freelancer	The threat hunter that does not belong to an organization and works primarily as a contractor.
		Consultant	The threat hunter works for an organization that provides threat hunting services to clients.
		Internal	The threat hunter works as part of a security team of an organization and hunts within the environment of that organization.
	Role	Threat Hunter	The baseline role of threat hunter with no responsibility to manage peers.
		Senior Threat Hunter	Threat hunter with more experience and provides support for less experienced peers but has no responsibility to manage peers.
		Team Lead	Head of team with responsibility to lead the team in hunting activities but does not manage the team outside of hunting.
		Technical Manager	Manages the team outside of hunting activities (administrative). Could also manage threat hunting activities. A technical manager can be a team lead but a team lead cannot be a technical manager.
Categorical Dimensions	Hunting Experience	1	1 - 4 years of experience.
		2	5 - 9years of experience.
		3	10 - 19 years of experience.
		4	20+ years of experience.
	Learning Strategies	Self Taught	The threat hunter learns primarily through teaching themselves from resources.
		Trial and Error	The threat hunter learns primarily by trying and failing in secure environment.
		Formal Certification	The threat hunter learns primarily through courses and formal training.
		Mentorship and Collaboration	The threat hunter learns primarily through working with peers or a mentor and getting feedback.
	Location	Remote	The threat hunter works entirely from a non-office setting / from home.
		Hybrid	The threat hunter works both remotely and in an office setting.
		Office	The threat hunter works entirely from an office setting.
		Hunting Style	Proactive
Reactive			Response to attacks is done as they appear.
	Hunting Process	Ad Hoc	The team or individuals hunt by following threats and the path they follow rather than a prescribed procedure.
		Procedural	The hunting style is to follow a protocol on how to investigate specific threats (playbook).
	Cognitive Approach	Intuitive / Creative	The threat hunter uses gut feeling and intuition to navigate tasks and thinks outside of the box to solve problems.
		Analytical / Methodological	The threat hunter has a process they follow when they navigate tasks and use logical reasoning to solve problems.
	Collaboration Mode	Individual	Hunting is done individually.
		Team	Hunting is done as a team.
	Validation of Findings	Peer-Peer	The threat hunter validate their findings by checking with their peers.
		Resources	The threat hunter validates their findings by checking resources.
	Process Initiation	Hands-on	The threat hunter is customizing their tools and writing their own queries and scripts to get what they want from their tools.
		Tool-led	The threat hunter's workflow is derived from the existing tools functionality.
	Tool Quantity	One tool	Hunts are done with only one tool.
		10+	Hunts are being done using 10 or more tools.
	Tooling Landscape	Commercial	The tools being used are predominantly commercially produced threat hunting products.
		Built in-house	The tools being used are built by the threat hunter or the team. (For THs that work for companies creating and using commercial software it would still be considered commercial)
	Availability of Resources	Open source	Resources used by threat hunter are open source.
		Private intel	Resources used by threat hunter are from a private source.
	Formality of Resources	Casual	Resources used by threat hunter are like blogs, feeds, or social media and are not peer reviewed.
		Formal	Resources used by threat hunter is formal articles or literature often peer reviewed.
	Motivation	Intrinsic	The threat hunter is motivated to do their work by intrinsic things such as a sense of accomplishment, helping others, or fighting for a cause.
		Extrinsic	The threat hunter is motivated to their work by extrinsic things such as salary or recognition.

TABLE 5: Definitions of the dimensions created.

Persona	Description
Thomas <i>Senior TH</i>	Thomas has over 25 year of experience as a security professional. He is involved in many online communities. He has a well-crafted toolkit of five to seven key tools. He hunts proactively and tries to be always one step ahead of attackers. He uses many resources to validate his hunting hypotheses and prefers to use tools he's built and customized himself. Thomas is motivated by keeping the organizations he protects safe and highly values educating clients and the public on proper security hygiene. The main pain points he is affected by are screen fatigue, restricted data availability, and diverse client systems.
Jay <i>New TH</i>	Jay holds a Master's degree in IT security and has been a TH for two years. He has specialized skills and enjoys writing scripts to automate the steps of his hunting. His hunting style is procedural and reactive. He uses the organization's ticketing systems to communicate with his team and clients. He uses a large range of tools to assist his tasks and likes to be hands-on. He is motivated by hard work, advancing his career and financial incentives. The main pain points that affect Jay are slow tools, information overload, diverse communication styles, and context switching.
Olivia <i>TH Team Lead</i>	Olivia has seven years of cyber security experience and has SANS certification gained from mentorship she received. She is a senior member of her hunting team and provides guidance and feedback for her peers. Olivia uses a small but carefully curated toolkit to hunt and uses a more proactive hunting style. She works in an <i>ad hoc</i> manner and is very intuitive and creative in her work. She work primarily with private resources such as internal intelligence. Olivia is highly motivated by helping others and having a strongly connected team. The main pain points that affect her are diverse customer systems, context switching, limited support from her organization and working with many different personalities.
Ren <i>TH Technical Manager</i>	Ren works as a consultant for clients that are external to their organization. They are a hands-on manager that works closely with their team and their clients. They work in a hybrid environment and runs quarterly meetings with their clients to report the critical findings their team have uncovered. Ren is good at communicating highly technical information in an approachable way. They pride themselves on building diverse teams that are composed of driven and passionate individuals. They are motivated by reaching goals set out by their team, clients, and organization. Some pain points that affect Ren are the lack of data availability, overly complex tools, diverse client systems, and screen fatigue.

TABLE 6: Four Threat Hunter Personas.